

ESSENTIAL OIL FROM THE LEAVES OF *BLUMEA LACERA*

By K. K. DASLAS AND S. S. DESHAPANDE

The essential oil from the leaves of '*Blumea lacera*' consists of 66% cineol, 10% *d*-fenchone and about 6% citral.

The plant '*Blumea lacera*' known in Hindi as "Kakronda" and in Sanskrit as "Kukradru" is indigenous to India. It grows in fields near Agra and generally throughout North India. It is a small bushy plant with wooly leaves and belongs to the family of Compositae. It is regarded as highly medicinal and is specially used to cure skin diseases.

Another species, *Blumea balsamifera*, has been worked out by Jonas (*Schimmel's Ber.*, 1909, April, p. 152) who mentions the cineol, limonene, *l*-borneol, *l*-camphor etc. as the chief components of its essential oil.

As will be seen from the following, the composition of the oil extracted by us from *Blumea lacera* is different.

The essential oil was obtained by steam distillation of its leaves in 0.5% yield. It is a greenish yellow oil with following properties:— d_{20}° , 0.982; n_D , 1.490; $[\alpha]_D^{20}$, 31.6°.

The oil (60 c.c.) was distilled at reduced pressure (30 mm.) and the following fractions were collected:—

(I) 78°-80°, 40 c.c. (II) 80°-120°, 10 c.c. (III) 120°-135°, 6 c.c.

Fraction (I) was strongly odorous. At atmospheric pressure it distilled almost wholly at 178°. It absorbed bromine but gave no nitrosite or nitrosyl chloride. It did not reduce Fehling's solution or ammoniacal silver nitrate and did not form any semicarbazone. As its odour resembled that of eucalyptus oil the presence of cineol was suspected and was confirmed on examination. Thus the fraction formed a solid additive compound with syrupy phosphoric acid (cf. Kebler, *Amer. J. Pharm.*, 1898, 70, 492). It also forms a crystalline compound with resorcinol melting at 85-87° and on two crystallisations at 87-90° (Baeyer and Virck, *Ber.*, 1902, 35, 1209, mention m.p. 80-85°). On warming this product with aqueous caustic soda the regenerated cineol, obtained by extraction, boiled at 178°. Identity of this fraction with cineol was finally confirmed by comparing the above tests with genuine sample of cineol obtained from eucalyptus oil. The percentage of cineol in the oil calculated from the weight of the fraction is 66.

Fraction (II) (10 c.c.) was redistilled at 30 mm. pressure when 6 c.c. passed at 91° and the remaining 4 c.c. of the contents distilled within a wide range of 92°-120°. The portion passing at 91° appeared to be a distinct individual and when it was distilled at atmospheric pressure it boiled at 192°. Analysis of this fraction corresponds with the composition $C_{10}H_{16}O$.

The component $C_{10}H_{16}O$ does not reduce Fehling's solution or ammoniacal silver nitrate and also does not form any solid derivative characteristic of hydroxyl group. It, however, forms an oxime, m.p. 163° and a semicarbazone, melting at 184° and on recrystallisation at $186-87^{\circ}$. The composition of the semicarbazone determined by analysis corresponds with the semicarbazone of the ketone, $C_{10}H_{16}O$.

From the boiling point and results of analysis of the ketone and from the melting point of its oxime and that of its semicarbazone the ketone is identified as *d*-fenchone (b.p. $192^{\circ}-194^{\circ}$; oxime, m.p. 163° ; Mahla and Tiemann, *Ber.*, 1896, 29, 2818); semicarbazone, m.p. $186-87^{\circ}$ (Rimini, *Gazzeita*, 1900, 30, 600). Calculated from the amount of this fraction the ketone forms 10% of the total oil.

Fraction (III) boiling between 120° and $135^{\circ}/30$ mm. proved to be unstable and could not be distilled at atmospheric pressure without polymerisation. However, on rapid distillation a small amount distilled at 230° . It proved to be an aldehyde as it reduced Fehling's solution and formed a sodium bisulphite compound. From its boiling point and the ease with which it polymerised it was suspected to be citral. The bisulphite compound was more easily prepared by Tiemann's method (*Ber.*, 1898, 31, 3311) and the method suggested by Tiemann for preparing semicarbazone from bisulphite compound in the case of citronellal (*ibid.*, p. 3307) was used in the present case with the modification that free acetic acid was used. This gave a semicarbazone melting at 163° (semicarbazone of citral- α melts at 163°). The identity of citral in fraction (III) was confirmed by comparing the results of these tests with a genuine sample of citral obtained from lemon grass oil. From the weight of the fraction the percentage of citral in the oil is about 6.

TABLE I

Fraction No.	B.p. (30 mm.)	Vol.	Yield.	Properties	
				B p. at atmospheric pressure	M.p. of derivatives.
I	$78^{\circ}-80^{\circ}$.	40 c.c.	66%	178°	Compound with resorcinol ($87^{\circ}-90^{\circ}$)
II	$80^{\circ}-120^{\circ}$.	10 ↓ Refractionated ↓			
(a)	91°	6 c.c.	10%	192°	Oxime (m.p. 163°). Semicarbazone, m.p. $186-87^{\circ}$
(b)	$92^{\circ}-120^{\circ}$.	3	—	—	—
III	$120^{\circ}-135^{\circ}$	6	6	About 230° with polymerisation	Semicarbazone, m.p. 163°

E X P E R I M E N T A L

Isolation of the Oil.—The essential oil was obtained by steam distillation of the leaves from a copper still fitted with a spiral copper condenser. The steam distillate was extracted with carbon tetrachloride, the extract dried and the solvent removed on a water-bath. The greenish yellow oil obtained in 0.5% yield has the properties given in the introductory part.

Fractionation of the Oil.—The fractions obtained by distilling 60 c.c. of the oil at 30 mm. pressure, their boiling ranges, percentage yield and properties are given in Table I.

Identification of Cineol in Fraction (I): Cineol-phosphoric acid Addition Compound.—To the fraction (2.5 c.c.), cooled by ice and salt, was added dropwise 1 c.c. of syrupy phosphoric acid (*d* 1.75), similarly cooled. Thorough mixing is necessary. The addition product immediately separated as a pasty solid which became harder on further cooling.

Cineol-resorcinol Addition Compound.—Resorcinol (0.5 g.) was added to 2.5 c.c. of the fraction and the mixture warmed until resorcinol went into solution. On cooling, the addition product separated in rhombic plates. On filtering, washing with a little alcohol and drying the compound melted at 85-87°. Two crystallisations from alcohol raised the melting point of the product to 87-90°.

Identification of d-Fenchone in Fraction (II).—The fraction boiling at 91°/30 mm. or at 192° at atmospheric pressure was analysed. (Found: C, 79.2; H, 10.2. $C_{10}H_{16}O$ requires C, 78.9; H, 10.5 per cent).

Oxime of d-Fenchone.—To alcoholic solution of this fraction was added aqueous solution of hydroxylamine hydrochloride, neutralised with equivalent amount of caustic potash. After filtering off the potassium chloride and refluxing on a water-bath for 2 to 3 hours the solution was poured on a watch glass. The oxime which separated was freed from adhering liquid and on crystallisation from alcohol and ethyl acetate it melted at 163°.

Semicarbazone of d-Fenchone.—On adding the fraction to an aqueous concentrated solution of semicarbazide hydrochloride and sodium acetate and on occasional shaking the semicarbazone began to separate after two days and on standing for one week the separation was complete. On crystallising from dilute alcohol it melted at 184°. Further crystallisation, twice from the same solvent, raised the melting point to 186-87°. (Found: C, 63.1; H, 10.9; N, 19.6. $C_{11}H_{16}ON_2$, requires C, 63.1; H, 9.0; N, 20.0 per cent).

Sodium Bisulphite Compound and Semicarbazone of Citral in Fraction (III).—A cold saturated solution of sodium sulphite was added to this fraction kept cool by ice. On

gradually adding acetic acid and vigorous shaking crystals of the bisulphite compound began to separate. These were filtered, freed from adhering oil and dissolved in excess of water. On adding a concentrated solution of semicarbazide hydrochloride, sodium acetate and free acetic acid and on cooling thoroughly, the semicarbazone began to separate, which on crystallisation from dilute alcohol melted at 163° .

CHEMICAL LABORATORY,
AGRA COLLEGE, AGRA.

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